

Laboratory Assessment of the Efficacy of Some Biopesticides on Aspects of the Life Performance of the *Callosobruchus maculatus*

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Abstract:

Callosobruchus maculatus, the Southern Cowpea Beetle, is one of the most damaging pests that feeds on stored seeds, severely reducing their nutritional content by compromising their quality and marketability. It is critical to identify a viable substitute for chemical pesticides, which not only have high costs but also numerous detrimental effects on both humans and the environment, as a result of the beetles' development of resistance to them. Therefore, the goal of the current study was to employ various biopesticides made from entomopathogenic fungus, which are fungi that feed on insects, and investigate the potential effects of these pesticides on the life

performance of the *C. maculatus*, which is significant for both nutrition and the economy. The study aimed to find a promising alternative to chemical pesticides by using biopesticides derived from entomopathogenic fungi. The results of the current laboratory study showed a significant effect of the two biopesticides, *L. lecanii* and *M. anisopliae*, in increasing the mortality rate of eggs and adult stages of the *C. maculatus*. After 9 days of exposure to the biopesticide, *M. anisopliae* produced the maximum mortality rate for both eggs and adults at a concentration of 5×10^7 g/L. The biopesticides *M. anisopliae* and *L. lecanii* were exposed to the eggs and adults that had the lowest death rate one day later. Based on the current study's findings, it can be said that using the biopesticides *M. anisopliae* and *L. lecanii* can help control the Southern Cowpea Beetle and lessen the need for chemical pesticides.

Keywords: Biopesticides, *Callosobruchus maculatus*, *Lecanicillium lecanii*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*.

Introduction

Cowpea seeds are often stored after harvest for use the following season, at which time they become vulnerable to storage pests, including the Southern Cowpea Beetle (*Callosobruchus maculatus* F) (Nisar et al., 2022). These insects, which belong to the *Chrysomelidae* family of the order Coleoptera, are regarded serious pests of stored crop seeds. They infest several legumes, including cowpeas, chickpeas, lentils, mung

beans, and soybeans, inflicting significant harm. The infestation starts in the field and spreads to storage, where the beetles complete their life cycle, reproduce, and devour the seeds, lowering their nutritional value and germination rate (R. K. Mahmood, 2017; Nisar et al., 2022)

Several research have demonstrated herbicides' negative impacts on non-target crop varieties (Shahzad et al., 2018). Pesticides' effects on plants can pose food safety risks and result in

economic losses. Due to the high pest infestation rate of cowpeas, farmers frequently spray insecticides such as fipronil, cyfluthrin, cypermethrin, pyridaben, and pyrimethanil to protect the crop ((Wang, Li, Zhang, & Ji, 2024). However, the widespread use of these insecticides in storage facilities has resulted in considerable difficulties, such as health risks for handlers, insect resistance, and expensive prices (van Den Berg, Velayudhan, & Yadav, 2021).

Despite specific recommendations for the use of chemical pesticides, there is an urgent need to create new pest management approaches that are safe and environmentally acceptable.

Plant-based insecticides, physical approaches, and microbiological products can be used as alternatives to conventional chemical pesticides (Ngegba, Cui, Khalid, & Zhong, 2022); Aimad et al., 2022). As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the usage of biopesticides that are safe for humans.

Material and Methods

Adult *C. maculatus* beetles were collected from Diwanayah Governorate's local markets and raised in a laboratory using healthy, uninfested cowpea seeds. The seeds were packed in 800 mL plastic bottles, 200 g per bottle. To breed the beetles, bottles were wrapped with fabric and placed in an incubator at $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $70\pm 5\%$ relative humidity (Bhalla, Gupta, Lal, Kapur, & Khetarpal, 2008). To prevent earlier infestations, newly emerged adult pairs were isolated from the old colonies and transferred to clean, frozen cowpea seeds (Singh, 2020). The biopesticides were obtained from the Department of Plant Protection, Ministry of Agriculture, Baghdad, Iraq. A concentration of 5×10^7 g/L was used for each biopesticide, with a control treatment using only distilled water. Egg mortality rate and adult mortality rate were measured.

Eggs from newly mated adults were retrieved within 24 hours. Every treatment, including the

control, was repeated three times. A 1 ml spray of the 5 g/L biopesticide solution was administered to the eggs from a 15 cm distance. Eggs were incubated at $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $70\pm 5\%$ relative humidity. The hatching percentage was measured over 1, 3, 6, and 9 days. Newly emerged adult beetles (24 hours old) were separated into sexes. Every treatment, including the control, was repeated three times. The adults were sprayed with a 1 mL spray of the 5 g/L biopesticide solution from a distance of 15 cm. The adults were then incubated at $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $70\pm 5\%$ relative humidity. The adult mortality % was measured during one, three, six, and nine days.

The factorial experiment was carried out using a completely randomized design (CRD). The data was analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Statistix version 10 software. Means were compared using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at a P-value of < 0.05 .

Results and Discussion

Effect of the Biopesticide *M. anisopliae* on Egg Mortality Rate

The results of this study show that the biopesticide *M. anisopliae* had a significant effect on both egg and adult mortality rates compared to the control treatment. As seen in Figure A1, the egg mortality rate reached 48.949% at a concentration of 5 g/L of the *M. anisopliae* biopesticide, while the control treatment had 0% egg mortality.

Furthermore, the duration of exposure to the fungal biopesticide had a significant impact on the percentage of egg destruction, as shown in Figure B1. The longer the exposure time, the higher the egg destruction percentage. The highest egg destruction rate of 34.854% occurred after 9 days of exposure, compared to the lowest rate of 15.934% on the first day of exposure.

These findings were consistent with those from several research. Wang et al. (2024) exposed substantial changes in the mortality rates of third-instar nymphs of the peach potato aphid (*Myzus persicae*) when treated with various entomopathogenic fungus, including *L. lecanii* and *M. anisopliae*. Similarly, Mohammed, Kadhim, and Hasan (2019) discovered that spore suspensions of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* caused the highest mortality rates, up to 81.1% and 77.7%, respectively, in third-instar larvae of the khapra beetle (*T. granarium*) after 10 days of

treatment, when compared to other fungi such as *L. attenuatum*, *C. globosum*, and *L. fumosorosea*. Furthermore, Mohammed, Kadhim, and Kamaluddin (2018) found that third-instar nymphs of *M. persicae* and cotton aphid (*A. gossypii*) had significantly different mortality rates depending on the fungal species used, with *L. lecanii* causing the highest mortality of 80% and 82%, respectively, while *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae*, and *C. globosum* resulted in mortality rates ranging from 35% to 67%.

Figure 1. Impact of *M. anisopliae* on Egg Mortality Rate

Effect of *Lecanicillium lecanii* on Egg Mortality Rate

The current study found that the fungicide *L. lecanii* had a significant effect on egg and adult mortality rates when compared to the comparison treatment. Figure A1 reveals that the egg mortality rate was 36,766% at a concentration of 5 g/L in the treatment with the biocide *L. lecanii* compared to 0% in the control treatment, as indicated in Figure (1B). The duration of exposure to the fungal biopesticide has a substantial impact on the rate of egg destruction; the longer the exposure, the higher

the percentage of egg destruction, as the highest rate of destruction during nine days from the time of exposure was 28.588%, compared to the lowest

Egg mortality rates are increased by the development of a direct pressure mechanism to enter the egg shell and the ability to release hydrolytic enzymes that break down the egg wall, such as chitinases, glucanases, and proteases (Chavan & Deshpande, 2013). This promotes spore germination while suppressing reactive oxygen species (PROS)(Yin et al., 2016).

The outcomes of this study are similar with prior research using fungi to counteract the role of eggs in insects. Thangavel, Palaniappan, Manickavasagam Pillai, Subbarayalu, and Madhaiyan (2013) showed the great perishability of *L. lecanii* spores against whitefly eggs *Aleurodicus dispersus* Russell, with a mortality rate of (97.8%) compared to *B. bassiana* (97.0%) after 15 days of treatment and giving *L. lecanii* fungus. The lowest hatchability of eggs (23.3%) after 10 days of therapy. Treviño-Barbosa et al. (2022) discovered that *L. lecanii* had a 92.86 percent mortality rate after 15 days of treatment with *Tetranychus urticae* dream eggs.

Aaltonen et al. (2014) discovered that *L. lecanii* spores might be reduced by treating eggs for the tomato leaf borer bug and the whitefly leaf miner, *Tota absoluta* (meyrick) and *B. tabaci* (genn.). The mortality rate increased with the concentration of mushroom spores, reaching 100% after 7 days of treatment. The presence of proteins, sugars, polar and nonpolar fats in the egg pulp's outer shell layer causes fungus spores to decompose these substances, allowing the fungus to produce enzymes such as protease lipase and spore germination, which uses these substances' energy as a primary source of continued germination (E. A. Mahmood & Tawfeeq, 2017).

Figure 2. Effect of the fungus *L. lecanii* on egg mortality rate over time

Effect of the Fungicide *M. anisopliae* on Adult Mortality Rate

The results in Figure 3 revealed that the fungicide has a considerable effect on adult mortality rates in *M. anisopliae*. In comparison to the control treatment, the greatest adult death rate reached 32.32% within 9 days, as shown in Figure 3.A1. The lowest rate was 12.13% for one day. The longer the exposure period, the greater the mortality rate.

Fungi have a distinct effect because of their capacity to enter the insect's body wall and emit enzymes that break it down. Enzymes such as chitinase, protease, and lipase aid fungi in penetrating the insect's interior cavity. Fungi's capacity to attach to the insect's body and create germination tubes and penetration organs varies, affecting its efficiency (Abdul & Tohma, 2020).

Biryol, Demirbağ, Erdoğan, and Demir (2022) found that the death rate of three-day-old nymphs of the peach insect *Myzus persicae* treated with numerous insect pathogenic fungi,

including *I. fumosorosea*, *B. bassiana*, *V. lecanii*, and *M. anisopliae*, differed significantly. According to Mohammed et al. (2019), after 10 days of treatment, *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* exhibited the highest mortality rates in *T. granarium* third-stage larvae, at 81% and 77.7%, respectively, when compared to *L. attenuatum*, *C. globosum*, and *L. fumosorosea*. Mohammed et al. (2018)

discovered that the death rates of three-day-old green peach bug nymphs, *M. persicae* and *A. gossypii*, varied significantly depending on the fungus used. While death rates for *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae*, and *C. globosum* varied from 35% to 67%, *L. lecanii* had the highest rates at 80% and 82%, respectively.

Figure 3. Shows the Effect of the Fungus *L. lecanii* on Insect Egg Mortality Rate

Effect of the Fungus *L. lecanii* on Adult Insect Mortality

The insect *M. anisopliae*'s adult mortality was greatly impacted by *L. lecanii*, according to the study. The highest adult death rate, 32.32% within 9 days, was illustrated in Figure 4A, while the lowest rate, 12.13% at 1 day, was shown. *L. lecanii* had an adult mortality rate that varied from 8.50% at day one to 27.13% at day nine. The results in this experiment recommend that adult mortality is increased by extended fungal exposure.

These results were in agreement with those of Sundaravalli, Varshney, Kandan, and Revathi (2022), who reported that *L. lecanii* had no effect on *Blaptostethus pallescens*, a predatory beetle that feeds *Frankliniella schultzei* flower thrips. Shahriari, Zibaee, Khodaparast, and Fazeli-Dinan (2021) report that *L. lecanii* showed the

lowest numbers of mortality among the four fungi tested against *Chilo suppressalis*, the rice stem borer. BORGIO (2008) also found that *L. saksenae* had no effect on a range of *Hemiptera* insects, such as *Nezara viridula*, *Dysdercus cingulatus*, and *Leptoglossus phyllopus*, despite the fact that *L. lecanii* spore germination and host infection require high humidity.

All things considered, *L. lecanii* might be a helpful biocontrol agent for some pests, nevertheless the target species and environmental conditions might limit how effective it is. Before applying it for pest control, extra research is necessary for the best possible results. As shown in Figure (5), the results also demonstrated that, when compared to *L. lecanii*, the biopesticide *M. anisopliae* had the highest adult death rate.

Figure 4. Effect of the Fungus *L. lecanii* on Adult Insect Mortality Rate

Figure 5. Shows the Highest Adult Mortality Rates for *M. anisopliae* and *L. lecanii*.

Conclusion

Each The Southern Cowpea Beetle is a harmful pest that attacks stored cowpea and legume seeds, reducing their nutritional value and marketability. With chemical pesticides becoming costly, environmentally hazardous, and more ineffectual due to resistance, viable alternatives are required. This study investigated biopesticides derived from entomopathogenic

fungus as a possible answer. Results showed that *L. lecanii* and *M. anisopliae* successfully enhanced mortality rates in both the egg and adult stages of *C. maculatus*. *M. anisopliae* at a concentration of 5×10^7 g/L showed the maximum efficiency. These findings indicate that fungal biopesticides, particularly *M. anisopliae*, could be a more sustainable and effective alternative to chemical

pesticides for managing the Southern Cowpea Beetle.

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